

POLAND

POLAND

ECONOMIC EFFECTS OF PROCESS AUTOMATION IN IMPROVING THE ACTIVITIES OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND SMALL BUSINESSES

Khudayarova Maftuna Shavkatovna

Mardonova Barno Asatulloevna

Assistant of Department of food and agricultural economics,
Samarkand branch of Tashkent State University of Economics., Uzbekistan.,
Samarkand

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7193989>

Abstract

The article emphasizes the need to automate the business process of small businesses, taking into account the risks that are possible in the current situation caused by the pandemic. The tasks are defined (reduction of accounting costs, organization of control over the activities of a small business entity, increasing the level of internal discipline in the company and elements of the activities of business structures that are subject to automation.

Key words: small business, automation, management, business process, digital economy, digital technologies, small business entity, Internet technologies

Introduction

The main goal of each business process is the achievement by a small business entity of specific optimization tasks. Internal and external parties of the company interact directly in financial and economic activities, interacting with each other (customers, control bodies, managers, employees). When problems arise in small businesses, in order to increase profitability, firms introduce automation and optimization of business processes. With their help, it is also possible to reduce business risks.

During the research, theoretical methods were used, namely: analysis and synthesis, the method of abstraction, induction and deduction, interpretation, in order to understand the mutual influence of factors that determine the dynamics of overall development. In addition, it should be noted about the use of empirical research methods: the study of literature and research results, observation, conversation, etc.

Research results and their discussion

The economic risks posed by the COVID-19 pandemic are the most discussed agenda today. There is a serious slowdown in production activity all over the world. As at the global level, the Russian economy has also reacted negatively to the epidemic, which has affected the economy deeply and is facing a crisis. One of the ways to support the effective activities of small businesses is business automation, which allows to improve the quality of the company's work, routine processes are abolished, profits increase. But each process has its own subtleties and nuances. Therefore, it is important to choose automated tools correctly.

Optimization of business processes is the basis for stable growth of the company. At the same time, attention should be paid to the specialization of a single business entity and individually find the best option for automating individual processes and management stages.

Automation of the processes of activity of most business structures is implemented according to an individual project, which is developed specifically for a single business entity. At the same time, it is possible to use internal audit aimed at reducing business risks and finding advantages.

At the same time, attention should also be paid to the effect of the introduction of automation of individual processes. For small businesses, the indicators of the effectiveness of automation of management processes should include:

- reduction of time for performing individual operations;
- shortening the period of signing contracts with contractors;
- reduction of calls to the company's support service;
- the growth of revenue from the sale of products, goods, works, services and others.

When choosing a CRM for business, the following features should be taken into account: the ability to maintain a customer base and fill in information; creating commercial proposals using built-in templates; planning tasks and tracking their implementation (both personal and employees); coordination and

control of the work of all members of the company and individual structures; interaction with customers, prompt receipt of reports and analytics; preparation of accounting documentation and registration of transactions; calling interested customers via internal telephony; sending emails and sending commercial offers; analysis of completed tasks set for a certain period of time.

Many small business owners are wary of considering additional software that requires additional costs. The expenses incurred pay off, because CRM allows you to increase productivity growth several times, reduce labor costs by 40%, increase sales several times and improve relationships with potential and existing customers by more than 70%.

If there are advantages, small businesses have a number of limitations that should not be overlooked. We are talking about a small budget, a small number of employees in the state and a simple company structure.

The rating of CRM systems for small businesses with a description of the functional features and advantages is presented in the table.

Brief description of CRM systems for small businesses

"Bitrix24"	A multifunctional tool designed for the verified management of the company. The service is designed to perform planned sales, maintain reports and save documentation. The multifunctional interface allows you to optimize your work with clients. Bitrix24 is the best free CRM system for business. The Bitrix24 system has a lot of advantages: warehouse accounting and graphical analytics; e-mail tracker for saving correspondence; integration with web applications, social networks and 1C; mobile version for Android, OC and iOS.
"Megaplan"	A program designed to optimize work with contractors as much as possible and aimed at increasing revenue from the sale of products, goods, works, services. It is mainly used by the NSR. for running a small business. Main advantages: instant technical support, intuitive interface, quick start, mail service, integration with 1C and telephony.

"Simple business"	A domestic project, indispensable for small businesses. The service is used to record customer information, save call history and all necessary documentation. Advantages: the possibility of personnel management and the presence of a chat for employees. In CRM "Simple Business", you can conduct a classic workflow, make mailing lists and use standard templates to speed up the process. There is a possibility of accounting accounting. The full tariff on a free basis is provided only for five employees.
Microsoft Dynamics CRM	A universal service designed for small business owners. It is used to increase the sales funnel. It is widely used in the field of trade, finance and education. The developer, Microsoft, has provided several categories for use:
Bpm'online sales	Sales – processing customer data from expressions of interest to purchase.
AmoCRM	Service – preliminary planning of the activities of each employee in order to optimize work activities and improve the quality of service.
Trello	Finance – control of the funds spent on advertising and net profit, conducting analytics of future sales.
Wrike	Marketing – providing an individual approach to each client of the company.
Mango Office	Microsoft Dynamics CRM allows you to attract potential customers and motivate stakeholders, develop and retain staff. The interface is so simple that even beginners have no difficulties when working with the service.

Conclusions

Automation of business processes for SMEs is necessary and relevant as one of the main advantages over competitors. For small business owners, the most affordable and simple CRM systems are provided, which do not require the purchase of expensive packages and have free free versions designed for 5-7

employees, which is quite enough. Entrepreneurs need to choose services based on the specifics and functional features.

With all the advantages of automation of business processes, it is necessary to highlight cases when it is not needed: if automation is more expensive than potential income; a small number of customers and narrow specifics of activity; there is no opportunity to ensure effective automation of business processes; business restructuring is planned.

References:

1. Modern information technologies for automation of business processes: monograph / A.S. Eropkina, Yu.A. Zobnin; Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education "Tyumen Industrial University". Tyumen: TIU, 2018. 155 p. ill.
2. Grigoriadi E.M. Fintech: new opportunities for financing small and medium-sized enterprises in Russia // Innovations and Investments. 2019. No. 4. pp. 196-199.
3. Feofilova T.Yu., Kohan R.S. Automation of evaluation of the internal control system by internal audit methods in the conditions of digital transformation of companies // Digital economy and industry 4.0: trends 2025. Proceedings of the scientific and practical conference with international participation. 2019. pp. 565-570.
4. Arapova I.A., Balashov A.G. Research of approaches to integration of automation solutions of processes of the marketing department of a small business enterprise // Innovative approaches to solving technical and economic problems. Proceedings of the International Conference. 2018. pp. 45-51.
5. Toland J. BPI, BPM and how they relate to new ERP implementations // Merit Solutions: A website of a global results-oriented business consulting organization. Access mode: <https://meritsolutions.com/resources/bpi-bpm-and-erp-white-paper/>.
6. Suchanek P., Baki R., Korzhenich A. Introduction of optimization methods in certain areas of production logistics // Forum Scientiae Economica. 2015. Volume 3(2). pp. 65-79.
7. Benotman Z., Belalem G., Neki A. Cloud computing model for optimizing the process of transport logistics // Transport and Telecommunications. 2017. Volume 18(3). pp. 194-206.

